

1D SQUEEZE FLOW ANALYSIS OF CHOPPED LONG FIBRE THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE

W. Ali, H.J.M. Geijselaers, R. Akkerman

University of Twente, Enschede, The Netherlands

Introduction

- Compression moulding is one of the process used for moulding of composites as shown in figure 1. Complex shapes can be manufactured with chopped flakes of thermoplastic composite using compression moulding.
- In order to manufacture predictable and reproducible products, the material flow behavior needs to be identified, modelled and characterized.

Figure 1. Typical compression molding cycle of discontinuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic molding compound.

Experimental work

- **Objective:** Study flow 1D squeeze flow of thermoplastic composite in the form of chopped flakes using compression molding.
- **Experiments:** 1D squeeze flow experiments in a mold which is partially filled on both sides.
- **Analysis:** Burn-off of composites material in Oven and TGA.

Figure 2. Figure 5: Left) Schematic of the experimental setup used for the 1D squeeze flow experiment. Right) (Left to right) Samples with increasing dwell time.

Conclusion

- The averaged results for the fibre mass fraction in the oven and TGA are shown in figure 3. It can be seen that there is **no significant trend for fibre mass fraction as a function of flow length**.
- Error bars show overlap and therefore there is no evidence that the compound behaves as a two-phase flow in the current range of applied shear rates. Therefore it can be assumed that the **flow field is single-phase and the fibre and matrix move together**.

Figure 3: Evolution of the fibre mass fraction in the flow direction.